

Parallelization and Performance Evaluation of Open-Source HEVC Codecs

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Received: date / Accepted: date

Abstract High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) was developed by the Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC) to replace the current H.264/Advanced Video Coding (AVC) standard, which has dominated digital video services in all segments of the domestic and professional markets for over ten years. In terms of rate-distortion, HEVC roughly doubles the compression performance of H.264/AVC, but at a cost of extremely high computational complexities during encoding. Parallelizing HEVC encoding is an efficient way of fulfilling this computational requirement. Since its standardization, several open-source HEVC video codecs have been developed with parallel encoding capabilities. This paper presents a rate-distortion/complexity analysis of the open-source HEVC codecs using objective measures of assessment in order to analyze their real parallelization capabilities. Experimental results show that DivX265 and x265 obtain the best parallel performance on average for the high-quality encoding scenario. In the case of the high-speed encoding scenario, x265 obtains the best parallel performance. In both scenarios, the coding efficiency of the encoders remains virtually unaffected regardless of the amount of parallelism.

Keywords HEVC Codecs · Open-Source · Evaluation · Parallelization · Computational Cost

1 Introduction

In the last years, H.264/Advanced Video Coding (AVC) [10] has been the most widespread video compression standard for all kinds of multimedia services, applications and scenarios. Nevertheless, the continuous market demands for

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a better quality of experience and the advent of new video formats such as the Ultra High Definition (UHD) resolution motivated the development of the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard [9]. Established by the Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC) in early 2013, HEVC is able to double the Rate Distortion (R-D) performance of H.264/AVC. This improvement in coding efficiency comes, however, at the expense of an extremely high computational complexity [15]. HEVC compensates this complexity overhead by specifying two principal, mutually exclusive, data-level parallelization strategies [16]: Tiles [14] and Wavefront Parallel Processing (WPP) [8]. They are by far the most popular schemes for implementing parallel processing in both software and hardware HEVC encoders.

With the aim of exploiting these parallelization strategies, several HEVC video codecs have been developed by the industry, but most of them are commercial products whose features and operating principles are kept confidential. Therefore, only open-source encoders are considered in this paper, with the exception of DivX265 [6], which although it is not strictly open-source, the encoder and its documentation have been made available by DivX. Among the existing open-source HEVC encoders, HEVC Test Model (HM) [11], as an HEVC reference codec, is able to achieve the best coding efficiency, but its object-based C++ implementation results in poor performance in terms of computational complexity. Hence, it is targeted for research and conformance testing rather than practical encoding. The commercially funded x265 [21] is the most well-known practical open-source HEVC encoder. It is based on HM C++ source code, which has been enhanced by extensive assembly optimizations, multithreading, and techniques from the open-source x264 encoder. Kvazaar [19] is an academic open-source HEVC encoder initiated and coordinated by [20]. It is licensed under GNU GPLv2 license. Kvazaar uses a reverse design approach compared with x265. In addition, Kvazaar is developed in C. Finally, HEVC Open MPEG Encoder (HomerHEVC) [4] is an open-source, real-time, multiplatform HEVC video encoder under LGPL license.

Except for HM, the rest of the open-source HEVC encoders support parallel processing. x265 and HomerHEVC offer WPP, but not Tiles. Kvazaar offers both Tiles and WPP. HomerHEVC, x265 and Kvazaar also provide further picture-level parallel coding schemes. WPP and Tiles are carried out by executing the software encoder on a multi- or many-core processor where the data processing flows are identical to each core.

Many previous works have been done to evaluate the R-D performance of HEVC and H.264/AVC standards. All the related works presented in the literature can be classified into two categories: 1) the comparison was performed between different encoders under the same coding standard, and 2) the comparison was conducted between HEVC and other coding standards like H.264/AVC using different coding modes. Note that almost all the papers and research are based on the reference encoders, e.g. HM and JM, which are only suitable for theoretical research. However, as many optimizations have been performed since the HEVC standard was released in 2013 [5, 12], it is necessary to analyze the performance (both in terms of compression and

speed) of practical encoders at their current state. Recently, a comparison focused on non-parallel versions of these encoders has been presented in [7]. For this reason, this paper focuses on a comparative evaluation of the open-source HEVC codecs using objective measures of assessment in order to analyze their real parallelization capabilities. The comparison was done using the settings provided by the developers of each codec.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 includes some technical background to the new HEVC standard. Section 3 presents the open-source HEVC video codecs under study, providing the experimental results in Sect. 4. Finally, Sect. 5 concludes the paper.

2 Technical Background

HEVC can be considered an evolution of the current H.264/AVC standard, since it maintains the same hybrid block-based approach used in all previous video compression standards. In addition, new tools have been introduced in HEVC that increase its coding efficiency compared with H.264/AVC [18].

One of the most important changes affects picture partitioning [13]. HEVC defines a new flexible Coding Tree Unit (CTU) structure which is a replacement of the Macroblocks (MBs), 16×16 pixel blocks, used in previous standards. With the aim of achieving an optimal adaptation to the content details, CTUs can vary from a size of 64×64 pixels, to something much smaller, as it can be iteratively partitioned into four square sub-blocks of half resolution, named Coding Units (CUs), with a minimum allowable size of 8×8 pixels. Therefore, a CTU can be further partitioned into four depth levels, from $d = 0$ for 64×64 CU to $d = 3$ for 8×8 CUs, having 4^d CUs in each depth level. Thus, a CU in depth level d can be denoted as $CU_{d,k}$, ($k = 0, 1, \dots, 4^{d-1}$), and the four corresponding sub-CUs as $CU_{d+1,4k+i}$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, 3, k = 0, 1, \dots, 4^{d-1}$). In a CTU of 64×64 , it can be observed that the total number of possible combinations of CUs is $(2^4 + 1)^4 + 1 = 83522$ showing the necessity of reducing the encoder complexity.

HEVC increases even more the flexibility of the CTU by defining two tree structures containing new unit types: the Prediction Units (PUs), and the Transform Units (TUs). For intra-picture prediction, a PU uses the same $2N \times 2N$ size as for the $CU_{d,k}$ to which it belongs, allowing it to be split into four $N \times N$ PUs only for CUs at the minimum depth level. Therefore, the PU size can range from 64×64 to 4×4 pixels. For inter-picture prediction, several non-square rectangular block shapes are available in addition to square ones, allowing eight different PU sizes ($2N \times 2N$, $2N \times N$, $N \times 2N$, $N \times N$, $2N \times nU$, $2N \times nD$, $nL \times 2N$, $nR \times 2N$).

The prediction residue obtained in each of the PUs is transformed using various TU sizes from 32×32 to 4×4 . In Fig. 1, an example of the partitioning is shown, depicting how a CTU is structured in a hierarchical tree where each CU branch ends in a leaf ($CU_{d,k}$) that is the root for the two new prediction

Fig. 1 Partitioning of CTU into CUs, PUs and TUs

Fig. 2 Partitioning of CTU into CUs (white), PUs (green) and TUs (black) applied to the BasketballPass sequence

and transform trees. Figure 2 shows the partitioning of CTU into CUs (white), PUs (green) and TUs (black) applied to the BasketballPass sequence.

It should be noted that a CU can be divided into different PUs (see Fig. 1), and each of these available PUs has to be evaluated for all intra/inter prediction modes available, and each of the obtained residual blocks can be transformed into up to three TU sizes. HEVC checks most of the PUs (inter and intra modes) to decide whether it should split a CU or not by choosing the best R-D case. Furthermore, in the case of inter prediction, for each of these PU partitions a motion estimation algorithm is called. This wide range of possibilities makes HEVC much more computationally expensive than its predecessor, H.264/AVC. HEVC introduces changes in other modules too, such as intra prediction (where a total of 35 different coding modes can be selected), new image filters or new transform sizes [18], among others. As expected, the

selection of the optimal partitioning for each CU/PU/TU is an intensive time consuming process due to the huge number of combinations that have to be evaluated.

The above analysis evidences the need to reduce the Rate-Distortion Optimization (RDO) complexity for the HEVC intra/inter prediction, in order to make real-time HEVC video codecs with the best possible performance. With the aim of reducing this huge RDO complexity, HEVC places special emphasis on hardware-friendly design and parallel-processing architectures. These parallelization approaches are Tiles [14] and WPP [8]. Basically, these parallelization approaches considered in HEVC rely on creating picture partitions and, thus, coding losses may appear due to breaking dependencies for prediction, CABAC context modeling, and/or slice header overhead.

2.1 Parallelization Techniques in HEVC

Previous video codecs, in particular H.264/AVC, have been parallelized using either frame-level, slice-level, or MB-level parallelism. Each of these approaches, however, has some limitations such as limited scalability, significant coding losses, or high memory requirements. To overcome these limitations, the new HEVC codec includes the previously mentioned parallelization techniques: Tiles and WPP.

On the one hand, Tiles are square or rectangular partitions where dependencies are broken across tile boundaries, entailing, hence, substantial coding losses, while making it possible to process them independently. Nevertheless, the deblocking and Sample Adaptive Offset (SAO) filters can still cross these boundaries. The number of tiles and their location can be defined for the whole sequence or changed from picture to picture.

On the other hand, WPP allows the pictures to be partitioned in rows, each of which can be processed in parallel, whereas entropy encoding and prediction are allowed to cross partitions to minimize coding losses. However, coding dependencies make it necessary to have a delay of, at least, two CUs between consecutive rows in a similar way to segmentation in a computer architecture. For this reason, not all the processes can start encoding these rows at the same time, which introduces the so-called “ramping inefficiencies” at the beginning and at the end of a frame, not allowing a parallel encoder/decoder to reach its peak performance. Both techniques, Tiles and WPP, are depicted in Fig. 3.

Tiles and WPP have different merits and disadvantages. While WPP is generally well-suited for the parallelization of the encoder and the decoder due to its high number of picture partitions with low compression losses, the amount of parallelism with Tiles is not fixed, as the number of regions in which a frame is divided may vary. Additionally, WPP does not introduce artifacts at partition boundaries as is the case for Tiles. WPP has almost no effect on the analysis and compression of each CTU and so it has a very small impact on compression efficiency relative to Tiles. The compression loss from

(a) Tiles partitioning

(b) WPP partitioning

Fig. 3 Partitioning and processing order of Tiles (a) and WPP (b)

WPP has been found to be less than 1% in most of the tests. To simplify the implementation, it is not possible to use Tiles and WPP simultaneously in the same compressed video sequence.

3 Open-Source HEVC Video Codecs

With the aim of reducing this high computational complexity, several sub-optimal (from the coding efficiency point of view) open-source HEVC encoders have been developed by the industry.

Among the existing open-source HEVC encoders, HM [11] as an HEVC reference codec is able to achieve the best coding efficiency. The HM software includes both encoder and decoder functionality. Reference software is useful in aiding users of a video coding standard to establish it and educate them, as well as demonstrating the capabilities of the standard. However, its object-based C++ implementation results in poor performance in terms of computational complexity. HM encoder does not support parallel processing. Hence, it is targeted for research and conformance testing rather than practical encoding.

x265 [21] is a commercially funded open-source implementation of the H.265/HEVC compression standard. The x265 codec is available under the GNU GPL v2 license. The x265 team has licensed the rights to port and adapt x264 for use in x265. Most of the video encoding algorithms developed for x264 have been incorporated in x265, including rate-control functions, the look-ahead function, macroblock tree, b-pyramid and adaptive quantization.

It is based on HM C++ source code which has been enhanced by extensive assembly optimizations and multithreading techniques. For parallel encoding, x265 offers two schemes: WPP and frame-threading processing. In x265, WPP is enabled by default since it not only improves computational performance at encode but it also makes it possible for the decoder to be threaded. Frame threading is the act of encoding multiple frames at the same time. x265 works around this problem by limiting the motion search region within the reference frames to just one CTU row below the coincident row being encoded. Thus a frame could be encoded at the same time as its reference frames as long as the latter are at least one row ahead. By default, frame parallelism and WPP are enabled together. The number of frame threads used is auto-detected from the (hyperthreaded) CPU core count.

Kvazaar [19] is an academic open-source HEVC encoder initiated and coordinated by [20] with the following primary goals: 1) coding efficiency close to HM, 2) modular structure to ease its parallelization and portability, and 3) excellent source code readability and documentation. To obtain these objectives with the highest possible encoding speed and with minimal computation/memory resources, Kvazaar has been developed from scratch in C. This unique approach uses the object-based C++ implementation of HM as a reference for its encoding scheme and individual algorithm implementations, but it adopts completely new data and function call tree structures. For parallel encoding, Kvazaar offers three schemes: Tiles, WPP, and picture-level parallel processing. Picture-level parallel processing can be utilized jointly with tiles and WPP. Kvazaar parallelization is implemented using a thread pool with a single CTU as the smallest work unit. The CTUs are put in a queue in the order in which they would be processed in a single threaded case, and the free worker threads always select the first CTU with no dependencies for processing.

HomerHEVC [4] is an open-source, real-time, multiplatform H.265/HEVC video encoder under LGPL license. The current features in its version 2.0 are: multiplatform (Linux, Windows), 8 bit-depth, intra and baseline profile, multiple references for IPP, all intra prediction modes, $2N \times 2N$ and $N \times N$ inter prediction modes, all prediction sizes, all transform sizes, half pixel and quarter pixel precision motion estimation, rate control, deblocking filter and SAO. Several SSE42 optimizations are also implemented. For parallel encoding, HomerHEVC offers two schemes: WPP and frame based parallelization. By default frame parallelism and WPP are enabled together. The number of default WPP and frame threads used are ten and three, respectively.

Finally, although it cannot be considered an open-source encoder, DivX and NeuLion solutions are powering the professional creation, secure distribution, and multi-screen playback of high-quality video for leading companies around the world [6]. The latest version of DivX265 has improved both encoding speed and efficiency dramatically. It provides four different encoding modes (presets) and WPP is employed to accelerate its coding speed. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the open-source HEVC codecs presented in this section.

Table 1 Open-Source HEVC Video Codecs Characteristics

Encoder	Version	Parallelization Strategies	Programming Language	Specific Optimizations
HM	16.6	N/A	C++	N/A
HomerHEVC	2.0	WPP Frame based	C	SSE4.2 optimizations
Kvazaar	0.8.3	WPP-Tiles Picture-level parallel processing	C	N/A
x265	1.9	WPP Frame-threading processing	C++	Assembly and x264 optimizations
DivX265	1.5	WPP Picture-level parallel processing	C/C++	Assembly optimizations

4 Rate-Distortion/Complexity Analysis

4.1 Encoding Parameters

This section aims to evaluate the real parallelization capabilities of the open-source HEVC codecs detailed in this paper using a rate-distortion/complexity analysis. The parameters used for each encoder are listed in Table 2. Our experiments rely on the default configuration of HM, which is used as an anchor for the obtained results. With regard to the rest of the open-source HEVC codecs under study, the evaluated presets are *veryslow* (high-quality encoding) and *ultrafast* (high-speed encoding). In practical applications, both high compression and fast coding are desired for video coding. They represent the slowest and fastest practical presets of them, respectively.

It should be noted that as not all the encoding parameters can be specified, and the default parameters of HM may be quite different from those of x265, HomerHEVC, Kvazaar and DivX265, the evaluation can only draw a rough picture of the current open-source HEVC encoders. However, we believe the R-D complexity evaluation can still provide a helpful reference for practical applications.

The hardware platform used in the experiments is composed of an Intel® Xeon® E5-2630L v3 octa-core CPU running at 1.80 GHz, 16 GB of main memory. The encoders were compiled with GCC 4.8.5-4 and executed on CentOS 7 (Linux 3.10.0-327). Turbo Boost was disabled to achieve the reproducibility of the results.

Due to Tiles strategy not being implemented in all open-source HEVC codecs under study, this paper focuses mainly on WPP and frame-thread parallelization strategies for the benchmark.

Table 2 Command line parameters

Encoder	Parameters
HM	-c (encoder configuration file) -c (sequence configuration file) --IntraPeriod=(intra period) --QP=(qp)
HomerHEVC	-widthxheight (resolution) -n_frames (frames) -frame_rate (fps) -bitrate_mode 0 -qp (qp) -gop_size (0 for AI, 1 for LP, 2 for RA) -intra_period (intra period) -n_enc_engines 3 -n_wpp_threads 10 -performance_mode (preset)
Kvazaar	--input-res (resolution) -n (frames) --input-fps (fps) --qp (qp) -p (intra period) --gop (8 for RA, lp-g4d4r4t1 for LP) --threads (2 for 2 cores, 4 for 4 cores, 8 for 8 cores) --wpp --preset (preset)
x265	--input-res (resolution) -f (frames) --fps (fps) --qp (qp) --keyint (intra period) --bframes (0 for LP) --pools (2 for 2 cores, 4 for 4 cores, 8 for 8 cores) --frame-threads (1 for 2 cores, 2 for 4 cores, 3 for 8 cores) --p (preset)
DivX265	-s (resolution) -n (frames) -fps (fps) -I 1 -qp (qp) -aqo (preset)

In order to ensure a common framework for simulations, the experiments were conducted under the Common Test Conditions and Software Reference Configurations recommended by the JCT-VC [3] for Random-Access (RA) mode configuration. That recommendation specifies the use of four Quantization Parameter (QPs) (22, 27, 32 and 37) and a set of 18 test sequences classified in five classes, A to E, which cover a wide range of resolutions from the largest (2560×1600 pixels) to the smallest (416×240 pixels), and frame rates from 60 fps to 24 fps. All the sequences use 4:2:0 chroma subsampling and a bit-depth of 8 bits:

- Class A (2560×1600 pixels): Traffic (30fps) and PeopleOnStreet (30fps).
- Class B (1920×1800 pixels): Kimono (24fps), ParkScene (24fps), Cactus (50fps), BQTerrace (50fps) and BasketballDrive (60fps).
- Class C (832×480 pixels): RaceHorsesC (30fps), BQMall (60fps), PartyScene (50fps) and BasketballDrill (50fps).
- Class D (416×240 pixels): RaceHorses (30fps), BQSquare (60fps), BlowingBubbles (50fps) and BasketballPass (50fps).
- Class E (1280×720 pixels): FourPeople (60fps), Johnny (60fps) and KristenAndSara (60fps).

4.2 Metrics

The rate-distortion/complexity analysis was evaluated in terms of Computational Complexity Reduction (CCR) and R-D performance for all open-source HEVC codecs under study, and both of them were compared to the HM codec results used as reference. For the CCR measure, the Time Saving (TS) metric was computed following the Equation 1. In addition to Time Saving, in order

to have a more fair comparison, Speed-Up (SU) metric has been also used following the Equation 2.

$$TimeSaving(\%) = \frac{Enc.Time(Codec) - Enc.Time(HM_{16.6})}{Enc.Time(HM_{16.6})} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Speed - Up = \frac{Enc.Time(HM_{16.6})}{Enc.Time(Codec)} \quad (2)$$

Regarding the R-D performance, the average Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) metric was calculated for each luma ($PSNR_Y$) and chroma components ($PSNR_U$, $PSNR_V$) and for the full number of frames of each sequence. In order to obtain a global quality measure, the average PSNR of the three components, denoted as $PSNR_{YUV}$, was also computed. As mentioned above, the chroma subsampling format of the test sequences was 4:2:0, so the well-known $PSNR_{YUV}$ according to Equation 3 was used, which applies weight pondering to the PSNR obtained for each component. Those weights are recommended by the JCT-VC in [17] and they are considered a fair representation of the visual quality, which is more sensitive to the luminance stimulus than the chrominance.

$$PSNR_{YUV}(dB) = \frac{6 \cdot PSNR_Y + PSNR_U + PSNR_V}{8} \quad (3)$$

The $PSNR_{YUV}$ for the four QPs were used for the computation of the R-D performance by using the Bjontegaard Delta Rate (BDR) metric defined by ITU [1, 2] and recommended by the JCT-VC. The BDR provides the average difference between the R-D curves measured as a percentage of bit rate that is necessary to increase or decrease to achieve the same PSNR quality in both curves. In our simulation, a positive BDR means the encoded bit rate using the open-source HEVC codec under study is higher than the bit rate obtained with HM, thus it is denoted as the penalty in terms of bit rate.

Finally, in order to measure the real parallelization capabilities, the sequential algorithm of each open-source HEVC codec has been used as the reference algorithm to calculate the corresponding speed-up and coding efficiency values when WPP and frame-threading processing are enabled for 2, 4 and 8 cores in each codec.

4.3 Simulation Results

Table 3 shows the experimental results of the sequential open-source HEVC codecs under study compared with the HM reference software for the high-quality encoding scenario. It can be observed that HomerHEVC codec obtains the highest speed-up (time savings up to 98%) while increasing excessively the bit rate penalty by around 124%. On the contrary, DivX265 codec obtains the lowest bit rate penalty (19%) with a considerable speed-up (time saving by

around 80%). Table 4 shows the experimental results of the sequential open-source HEVC codecs under study compared with the HM reference software for the high-speed encoding scenario. In this case, x265 codec obtains the lowest bit rate penalty (117%) at the expense of obtaining the lowest speed-up (but with time saving around 98%), compared with the rest of HEVC codecs, which show an excessive bit rate penalty of over 150% or even 250%. High speed-ups are obtained by the open-source HEVC codecs using several suboptimal and reduced sets of prediction modes in the picture partitioning.

Figure 4 shows the trade-off between speed and quality for the HEVC video codecs under study when executing their sequential version in both scenarios (presets). It would have been desirable that the different HEVC video codecs under study obtained the best quality with the minimum speed requirements specified for the different presets. In reality, however, each codec has been tuned in a different way and, as a result, they result in a wide variation of average speed (across a range of bit-rates) and average quality that makes independent comparison on just quality or speed values misleading. Hence, the speed/quality trade-off comparison results give a more balanced view of how a particular encoder is placed. It can be observed that extracting the percentage of BDR improvement from any codec results in a substantial speed degradation. On the other hand, fundamental improvements to coding tools should allow a similar compression efficiency to be reached without such an exponential increase in computational complexity.

Tables 5 and 6 show the corresponding speed-up with respect to the sequential version of the codecs and coding efficiency values, when WPP and frame-threading processing are enabled for the high-quality encoding scenario. As can be seen, the HEVC codecs can reach speed-up values close to the ones from a parallel efficient algorithm (i.e. cores are almost fully utilized), providing that the frame size is large enough to exploit the available parallelism (see Class A, B and E). Accordingly, WPP obtains lower speed-up results with lower resolutions (see Class C and D). Generally, there is much less frame parallelism to exploit in lower resolutions than in higher resolutions due to the number of CTU rows available. For instance, Class A video sequences has 25 CTU rows available each frame while Class D video sequences has only 4 CTU rows. It should be noted that no bit rate penalty is paid when parallelization strategies are enabled in all HEVC codecs under study. Among the HEVC codecs, DivX265 and x265 obtain, on average, the best parallelization performance.

Tables 7 and 8 show the corresponding speed-up with respect to the sequential version of the codecs and coding efficiency values, when WPP and frame-threading processing are enabled for the high-speed encoding scenario. In this scenario x265 obtain, on average, the best parallelization performance. With regard to the coding efficiency, this speed-up has a negligible impact in terms of BDR with respect to the sequential version of the codecs.

Figures 5 to 9 show the frames per second obtained in the hardware platform used in our experiments, when one, two, four or eight cores are enabled for different classes of sequences and for both scenarios. Real-time encoding

Table 3 Speed-up (SU) and Coding Efficiency (BDR) results with respect to HM. High-Quality (HQ) encoding scenario

Class/Sequence		HomerHEVC		DivX265		Kvazaar		x265	
		SU	BDR (%)	SU	BDR (%)	SU	BDR (%)	SU	BDR (%)
A	Traffic	52.16	105.8	5.11	19.8	9.67	60.4	2.22	28.1
	PeopleOnStreet	59.10	51.1	5.72	10.0	3.42	45.7	1.55	22.0
B	Kimono	55.69	80.3	6.28	20.8	4.11	59.4	1.82	38.1
	ParkScene	51.59	100.5	4.89	23.0	6.72	57.6	1.96	33.3
	Cactus	56.12	107.2	5.18	16.6	4.56	77.3	1.97	44.7
C	BasketballDrive	60.02	82.3	5.82	15.2	3.13	76.3	1.58	52.3
	BQTerrace	55.19	182.0	4.77	25.2	7.71	120.7	1.97	43.5
	BasketballDrill	58.37	100.0	5.12	17.3	3.17	45.4	1.91	39.1
	BQMall	55.77	115.5	5.09	19.7	3.65	73.5	1.82	45.5
D	PartyScene	53.25	164.9	4.06	21.9	4.97	64.7	1.80	38.6
	RaceHorses	62.58	56.3	5.41	14.3	2.56	51.3	1.42	23.5
	BasketballPass	61.14	63.6	5.16	10.3	2.47	49.0	1.59	26.0
	BQSquare	48.97	334.4	3.90	33.0	9.41	126.7	1.91	45.4
E	BlowingBubbles	51.28	145.5	3.86	22.0	6.01	63.7	1.88	39.1
	RaceHorses	60.38	60.9	4.99	13.5	2.42	51.0	1.38	24.6
	FourPeople	56.35	124.7	5.82	17.3	13.41	50.2	2.89	37.9
	Johnny	58.91	197.1	6.62	22.1	22.16	76.7	2.68	48.2
	KristenAndSara	59.03	155.1	6.50	19.4	14.84	67.9	2.39	45.1
	Class A	55.63	78.4	5.41	14.9	6.54	53.1	1.89	25.1
	Class B	55.72	110.5	5.39	20.2	5.24	78.2	1.86	42.4
	Class C	57.49	109.2	4.92	18.3	3.59	58.8	1.74	36.7
	Class D	55.44	151.1	4.48	19.7	5.08	72.6	1.69	33.8
	Class E	58.10	158.9	6.31	19.6	16.80	64.9	2.65	43.7
	Average	56.44	123.7	5.24	19.0	6.91	67.6	1.93	37.5

is obtained when the frames per second obtained are above the frame rate of each sequence (see Subsection 4.1). As can be seen, when high-quality encoding scenario is used, no real-time encoding is possible even in video sequences with lower resolutions (see Class C and D) and with eight cores. When the high-speed encoding scenario is taken into account, and when eight cores are fully used, DivX265 is able to achieve real-time encoding performance for all resolutions classes 1920×1080 (29.7 fps), 832×480 (121.1 fps), 416×240 (264.6 fps), and 1280×720 (80.5 fps), except for the 2560×1600 resolution (17.5 fps).

Finally, the open-source HEVC parallelization strategies have several desirable properties. First, they achieve good scaling efficiency at moderate core counts. Second, the number of encoding threads can be chosen to match the processing capabilities of the computing hardware and the performance requirements. Third, the usage of more cores increases the throughput and, at the same time, reduces the frame latency, making the implementation both suitable for low delay and high-throughput scenarios.

Table 4 Speed-up (SU) and Coding Efficiency (BDR) results with respect to HM. High-Speed (HS) encoding scenario

Class/Sequence		HomerHEVC		DivX265		Kvazaar		x265	
		SU	BDR (%)	SU	BDR (%)	SU	BDR (%)	SU	BDR (%)
A	Traffic	114.54	135.9	429.63	155.2	180.14	214.5	79.75	92.9
	PeopleOnStreet	124.35	62.5	388.75	113.7	137.72	135.6	54.09	82.5
B	Kimono	114.99	112.6	326.66	99.2	150.90	178.1	59.53	63.9
	ParkScene	112.57	120.3	343.16	139.2	154.11	203.3	68.83	84.7
	Cactus	127.57	136.4	314.29	147.6	157.45	259.9	68.21	117.9
C	BasketballDrive	131.39	102.4	289.88	124.8	139.61	257.1	61.77	96.5
	BQTerrace	126.92	235.2	318.88	312.1	151.08	574.0	74.06	189.2
	BasketballDrill	134.67	121.6	398.29	142.8	156.63	158.7	70.28	114.6
	BQMall	119.89	140.5	350.65	198.9	131.58	280.8	71.03	139.8
D	PartyScene	130.28	201.1	352.25	238.0	115.92	313.9	63.76	133.9
	RaceHorses	141.82	72.8	334.24	154.1	118.37	202.0	53.89	115.9
	BasketballPass	124.39	75.5	320.34	128.4	123.24	157.8	59.65	98.3
	BQSquare	105.41	421.2	308.42	495.5	104.33	641.4	69.87	222.2
E	BlowingBubbles	118.70	181.4	319.53	209.6	117.74	268.7	68.63	132.5
	RaceHorses	126.03	73.8	308.29	156.9	110.70	186.8	51.85	115.9
	FourPeople	125.43	169.9	388.24	111.1	250.09	177.6	113.50	83.0
	Johnny	123.58	272.9	333.61	165.3	278.15	293.4	125.67	120.9
	KristenAndSara	122.50	208.0	351.07	140.9	271.98	252.0	113.65	106.8
	Class A	119.44	99.2	409.19	134.5	158.93	175.0	66.92	87.7
	Class B	122.69	141.4	318.57	164.6	150.63	294.5	66.48	110.5
	Class C	131.66	134.0	358.86	183.4	130.62	238.9	64.74	126.0
	Class D	118.63	188.0	314.14	247.6	114.00	313.7	62.50	142.2
	Class E	123.84	216.9	357.64	139.1	266.74	241.0	117.61	103.6
	Average	123.61	158.0	343.12	179.6	158.32	264.2	73.78	117.3

5 Conclusions

The HEVC standard achieves double compression efficiency compared with H.264/AVC at the cost of huge computational complexity. Parallelizing HEVC encoding is an efficient way of fulfilling this computational requirement. The parallelization algorithms considered in HEVC, such as Tiles or WPP, rely on creating picture partitions that can be processed concurrently in a multi-core architecture. This paper presents a rate-distortion/complexity analysis of the several open-source HEVC codecs in order to analyze their real parallelization capabilities. In their sequential versions, high speed-up are obtained (time savings up to 99%) by the open-source HEVC codecs using several suboptimal and reduced set of prediction modes in the picture partitioning, at expense of excessive bit rate penalties. On the other hand, for the high-quality encoding scenario, DivX265 and x265 obtain, on average, the best parallelization performance. In the case of the high-speed encoding scenario, x265 obtains, on average, the best parallelization performance. With respect to the coding efficiency, the obtained speed-up have a negligible impact in terms of BDR regardless the number of threads with respect to the sequential version of the

Fig. 4 Speed/Coding Efficiency trade-off for HEVC video codecs

Fig. 5 Frames per second for class A sequences (1, 2, 4 and 8 cores).

codecs. Finally, no real-time encoding is possible even in video sequences with lower resolutions when high-quality encoding scenario is used. On the contrary, in the high-speed encoding scenario, and when eight cores are used, DivX265 obtains real-time encoding for all classes of sequences, except for class A.

Table 5 Speed-up results for 2, 4 and 8 cores. High-Quality (HQ) encoding scenario

Class/Sequence	HomerHEVC			DivX265			Kvazaar			x265		
	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8
A Traffic	1.95	3.89	7.79	2.01	4.02	8.04	1.93	3.74	7.63	1.96	3.94	7.72
PeopleOnStreet	1.95	3.91	7.81	2.00	4.01	8.03	1.91	3.82	8.05	1.96	3.98	7.79
B Kimono	1.95	3.91	7.60	1.99	3.99	7.95	1.90	3.51	6.59	1.96	3.92	7.58
ParkScene	1.95	3.89	7.60	1.99	3.99	7.97	1.86	2.98	5.73	1.96	3.90	7.51
Cactus	1.96	3.91	7.63	2.00	3.99	7.99	1.90	3.38	6.11	1.96	3.99	7.74
BasketballDrive	1.94	3.91	7.62	2.00	4.00	7.95	1.90	3.48	6.93	1.96	3.98	7.72
BQTerrace	1.97	3.89	7.62	2.00	4.00	7.99	1.89	3.39	6.19	1.96	3.96	7.70
C BasketballDrill	1.83	3.55	4.37	1.96	3.61	4.81	1.87	3.52	3.75	1.90	3.70	5.27
BQMall	1.82	3.50	4.14	1.97	3.59	4.83	1.89	3.50	3.67	1.90	3.71	5.29
PartyScene	1.84	3.59	4.48	1.97	3.62	4.89	1.76	3.13	3.32	1.88	3.73	5.29
RaceHorses	1.84	3.58	4.62	1.97	3.65	4.89	1.86	3.74	4.47	1.89	3.83	6.04
D BasketballPass	1.52	1.50	1.34	1.69	2.23	2.28	1.81	1.98	2.04	1.67	2.22	2.86
BQSquare	1.53	1.63	1.40	1.73	2.37	2.44	1.85	2.07	1.97	1.68	2.30	3.10
BlowingBubbles	1.53	1.67	1.41	1.74	2.33	2.42	1.82	2.02	2.02	1.66	2.23	2.91
RaceHorses	1.55	1.71	1.42	1.76	2.34	2.44	1.87	2.16	2.37	1.69	2.46	3.08
E FourPeople	1.92	3.80	7.10	1.99	3.95	6.68	1.88	3.12	3.22	1.95	3.91	7.11
Johnny	1.91	3.79	6.83	1.99	3.97	7.15	1.92	3.72	4.87	1.91	3.87	7.42
KristenAndSara	1.92	3.80	6.81	1.99	3.97	7.07	1.83	3.43	3.91	1.91	3.88	7.31
Class A	1.95	3.90	7.80	2.00	4.01	8.03	1.92	3.78	7.84	1.96	3.96	7.76
Class B	1.95	3.90	7.61	1.99	3.99	7.97	1.89	3.35	6.31	1.96	3.95	7.65
Class C	1.83	3.55	4.41	1.97	3.62	4.86	1.85	3.47	3.80	1.89	3.74	5.47
Class D	1.53	1.63	1.39	1.73	2.32	2.40	1.84	2.06	2.10	1.68	2.30	2.99
Class E	1.92	3.79	6.91	1.99	3.96	6.97	1.88	3.42	4.00	1.93	3.89	7.28
Average	1.84	3.36	5.63	1.94	3.58	6.04	1.87	3.22	4.81	1.88	3.57	6.23

Table 6 Coding efficiency results for 2, 4 and 8 cores in BDR (%). High-Quality (HQ) encoding scenario

Class	HomerHEVC			DivX265			Kvazaar			x265		
	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8
Class A	78.7	78.6	78.7	14.9	14.9	14.9	53.1	53.1	53.3	25.1	25.1	25.1
Class B	110.5	110.5	110.5	20.2	20.2	20.2	78.2	78.2	78.2	42.4	40.4	40.4
Class C	109.3	109.3	109.2	18.3	18.3	18.3	58.8	58.8	58.8	36.7	36.4	36.4
Class D	151.1	151.2	151.2	19.7	19.7	19.7	72.4	72.4	72.4	33.8	33.6	33.6
Class E	159.1	159.1	159.0	19.6	19.6	19.6	64.9	65.0	65.0	43.7	44.4	44.4
Average	123.8	123.8	123.8	19.0	19.0	19.0	67.6	67.6	67.6	37.5	37.0	37.0

Acknowledgements This work was jointly supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Commission (FEDER funds) under the project TIN2015-66972-C5-2-R, and by the Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports under the grant FPU13/04601.

Table 7 Speed-up results for 2, 4 and 8 cores. High-Speed (HS) encoding scenario

Class/Sequence	HomerHEVC			DivX265			Kvazaar			x265		
	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8
A Traffic	1.95	3.85	7.65	1.69	3.27	5.43	1.97	3.69	8.25	1.98	3.98	7.87
PeopleOnStreet	1.95	3.90	7.76	1.82	3.54	6.33	1.94	3.77	8.22	2.01	4.02	7.95
B Kimono	1.97	3.90	7.27	1.83	3.46	5.97	1.96	3.57	7.92	1.96	3.94	7.77
ParkScene	1.94	3.83	7.08	1.78	3.37	5.82	1.95	3.42	7.89	1.94	3.92	7.70
Cactus	1.95	3.85	7.08	1.84	3.48	6.29	1.96	3.48	7.80	1.96	3.93	7.71
BasketballDrive	1.99	3.93	7.26	1.87	3.60	6.49	1.96	3.56	7.98	1.94	3.94	7.75
BQTerrace	1.95	3.83	7.12	1.84	3.45	6.29	1.91	3.48	7.85	1.90	3.91	7.66
C BasketballDrill	1.83	3.29	3.44	1.75	3.01	4.86	1.87	3.81	5.57	1.88	3.88	7.38
BQMall	1.81	3.25	3.41	1.77	3.03	4.94	1.90	3.96	5.42	1.87	3.89	7.45
PartyScene	1.81	3.29	3.77	1.78	3.09	5.00	1.87	3.88	6.08	1.89	3.88	7.42
RaceHorses	1.85	3.40	4.02	1.81	3.20	5.25	1.85	3.89	6.05	1.91	3.87	7.47
D BasketballPass	1.41	1.20	1.19	1.73	2.65	3.23	1.91	2.55	2.57	1.81	3.38	5.02
BQSquare	1.41	1.21	1.19	1.69	2.57	3.05	1.93	2.73	2.79	1.75	3.44	4.70
BlowingBubbles	1.41	1.21	1.18	1.68	2.56	3.00	1.96	2.88	3.05	1.76	3.40	4.63
RaceHorses	1.46	1.24	1.21	1.76	2.67	3.19	1.89	2.76	3.16	1.83	3.68	5.48
E FourPeople	1.91	3.64	6.43	1.64	3.04	4.95	1.91	4.02	6.00	1.87	3.86	7.49
Johnny	1.91	3.66	6.11	1.74	3.09	5.18	1.87	3.94	7.32	1.85	3.85	7.51
KristenAndSara	1.90	3.64	6.04	1.74	3.09	5.19	1.78	3.77	6.84	1.85	3.85	7.46
Class A	1.95	3.88	7.71	1.75	3.40	5.88	1.96	3.73	8.23	1.99	4.00	7.91
Class B	1.96	3.87	7.16	1.83	3.47	6.17	1.95	3.50	7.89	1.94	3.93	7.72
Class C	1.83	3.31	3.66	1.78	3.08	5.01	1.87	3.88	5.78	1.89	3.88	7.43
Class D	1.42	1.21	1.19	1.71	2.61	3.12	1.92	2.73	2.90	1.79	3.47	4.96
Class E	1.91	3.65	6.19	1.71	3.07	5.11	1.86	3.91	6.72	1.85	3.85	7.49
Average	1.81	3.18	5.18	1.76	3.13	5.06	1.91	3.55	6.30	1.89	3.83	7.10

Table 8 Coding efficiency results for 2, 4 and 8 cores in BDR (%). High-Speed (HS) encoding scenario

Class	HomerHEVC			DivX265			Kvazaar			x265		
	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8
Class A	99.8	99.7	99.7	134.5	134.5	134.5	175.0	175.0	175.2	87.7	87.7	87.7
Class B	141.7	141.6	141.8	164.6	164.6	164.6	294.5	294.5	294.1	110.5	110.5	110.5
Class C	137.0	137.0	137.0	183.4	183.4	183.4	238.9	239.0	239.0	126.0	126.0	126.0
Class D	189.6	188.8	188.4	247.6	247.6	247.6	313.5	313.5	313.5	142.2	142.2	142.2
Class E	216.2	216.0	216.0	139.1	139.1	139.1	241.0	240.8	240.8	103.6	103.6	103.6
Average	159.1	158.8	158.8	179.6	179.6	179.6	264.2	264.2	264.1	117.3	117.3	117.3

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Fig. 6 Frames per second for class B sequences (1, 2, 4 and 8 cores)

Fig. 7 Frames per second for class C sequences (1, 2, 4 and 8 cores)

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Fig. 8 Frames per second for class D sequences (1, 2, 4 and 8 cores)

Fig. 9 Frames per second for class E sequences (1, 2, 4 and 8 cores)

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